

BIOMASS TOP-CYCLE CHP WITH HIGH-TEMPERATURE HEAT PUMP COUPLING: ECONOMIC INSIGHTS FOR INDUSTRIAL DECARBONIZATION

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Abstract

Over half of the final energy consumed by the European industrial sector relied on carbon-emitting fuels in 2022. Biomass-based cogeneration technologies can efficiently adjust to varying industrial electricity and heat demands while contributing to substitute the use of fossil fuels. However, these technologies are best suitable for low-temperature heat applications, such as fuel drying or district heating. This study proposes a biomass cogeneration plant coupled with a high-temperature heat pump as a decarbonization solution for supplying medium-temperature industrial heat. We present an optimization model which combines the operation of cogeneration, heat pump and thermal units. Considering investment and operational costs, results allow us to evaluate the economics of the proposed configuration for a chemical processing industry and contribute to an in-depth understanding of technology options leading to an efficient use of renewable fuels.

1 Introduction

Aligned with the Paris Agreement's objective of limiting global temperature rise to 1.5°C, the European Commission signed in 2019 the European Green Deal, aiming to reach net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050 [1]. In 2021, the Commission set an intermediate target for reducing these emissions by at least 55% below 1990 levels by 2030 [2].

Although the growing share of renewable energy sources in electricity production contributes to abating climate change, more than 50% of 2022's final energy consumption in the European industrial sector was not in the form of electricity, but of carbon-emitting fuels and products [3]. Therefore, efforts to decarbonize industrial emissions should pursue solutions that efficiently use renewable fuels.

Combined heat and power (CHP) facilities maximize the use of energy in combustion processes by simultaneously providing electric and heat power. Particularly, scalable biomass-fired top-cycle (BTC) cogeneration technology can adjust to different demand profiles through highly efficient combustion [4]. In order to allow a broad range of biomass sources to be used as fuel, locally available feed is transformed into syngas through a gasification process.

Based on a previous scalability and replicability analysis [5], BTC's gasification process can adapt to different biomass feedstocks: while untreated wood, pruning, and olive pits present suitable quality conditions, other sources such as rice husk, straw and corn stover are less favourable. In the case of Spain, the availability of biomass suitable for this technology amounts to 82 TWh/year, the main source being forest residue biomass, followed by cereals straw, pruning, and olive pits.

Industrial heat quality requirements can significantly influence the suitability and economic viability of CHP technology

options [6], including BTC, which can provide up to 80°C temperature heat [4]. When medium temperatures (>100°C) are needed in industrial processes, a scalable BTC plant could be coupled with a high-temperature heat pump to lift the temperature of the flue gas condenser exit water to the required, medium-temperature quality.

The present study explores the economic viability of BTC plant in combination with a high-temperature heat pump for a Spanish chemical processing industry presenting a varying demand of electricity and steam at 12 bar and 190°C.

We present a mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) optimization model to determine the cost-optimal operation of a given plant supplying industrial electricity and heat demands. We use this mathematical approach to explore the optimal operation of the proposed setup while accounting for the investment costs and contrast the results with those of a plant comprising three conventional, natural gas-fuelled CHP units. The analysis is conducted for a whole calendar year corresponding to year 2023.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the model formulation and the case study comprising a Spanish industrial user for which the proposed coupling configuration is tested. The economic and operational results are presented in Section 3. Finally, we discuss our findings and suggest future research contributions in Section 4.

2 Methodology

This section is divided into two parts: firstly, we introduce the mathematical formulation of the proposed modelling approach and, secondly, we present a case study to illustrate the operational and economic performance of the BTC-heat pump coupling in an industrial application.

2.1 Model Formulation

The proposed model maximizes the total profit of a given plant to supply industrial electricity and heat demands for a time scope of a given amount of hours divided in hourly or shorter time steps. It has been developed to model the operation of conventional and biomass-based CHP and thermal technologies (e.g., boilers), and features the modelling of CHP-heat pump couplings. Moreover, the formulation features the inclusion of predefined start-up and shut-down power trajectories, which also allows to account for the gasification process in biomass-based technologies.

For quick reference, the main notation used is listed, as well as model parameters (uppercase) and variables (lowercase).

Nomenclature:

Notation	Description
Acronyms	
O	Total power output
P	Electric power output
Q	Heat power output
SD	Shut-down ramp process
SU	Start-up ramp process
Indexes	
$g \in G$	Generating units
$t \in T$	Hourly periods, running from t_0 to T
sdi	i^{th} interval of a shut-down trajectory
sui	i^{th} interval of a start-up trajectory
Subindexes	
c	Cogeneration units
h	Heat pumps

Parameters:

Parameter	Description	Unit
General		
C^{CO_2}	CO ₂ emission cost	€/tCO ₂
$C^{Q_{Exc}}$	Excess heat cooling cost	€/MWh
D_t	Duration of each period	h
EC_t	Electricity cost	€/MWh
EP_t	Electricity price	€/MWh
$GCap$	Grid connection capacity	MW
P_{d_t}	Electricity demand	MW
Q_{d_t}	Heat demand	MW
Generating units		
C_g^F	Fuel cost	€/MWh
COP_{gh}	Coefficient of performance	MW/MW
$ER_g^{CO_2}$	CO ₂ emission rate	tCO ₂ /MWh
η_g	Total efficiency	Per unit
$\bar{P}_g, \underline{P}_g$	Max and min electric output	MW
$PQ_{slope_{gc}}$	Slope of CHP P-Q line	MW/MW
$\bar{Q}_g, \underline{Q}_g$	Max and min heat output	MW
Start-up and shut-down ramp processes		
C_g^{SU}, C_g^{SD}	SU and SD fixed costs	€

D_g^{SU}, D_g^{SD}	Duration of SU and SD ramps	h
$O_{g,sui}^{SU}, O_{g,sdi}^{SD}$	Total output at the i^{th} interval of the SU and SD ramps	MW

Variables:

Variable	Description	Unit
$f_{t,g}$	Fuel consumption	MWh
$gO_{t,g}$	Total output above minimum	MW
$gP_{t,g}$	Electric output above minimum	MW
$gQ_{t,g}$	Heat output above minimum	MW
$o_{tot_{t,g}}$	Total output	MW
$p_{t,g}$	Electric output	MW
p_{buy_t}	Electric power bought at spot market	MW
$p^{fd}_{t,g}$	Electric power final dispatch	MW
$p^{in}_{t,gh}$	HP electric power consumption	MW
p_{sell_t}	Electric power sold at spot market	MW
$q_{t,g}$	Heat output	MW
$q_{exc_{t,g}}$	Excess heat	MW
$q^{fd}_{t,g}$	Heat power final dispatch	MW
$q^{in}_{t,gh}$	HP heat source input	MW
$q^{out}_{t,gh}$	HP heat sink output	MW
$u_{t,g}$	Commitment during period t	{0,1}
$v_{t,g}$	Start-up in period t	{0,1}
$w_{t,g}$	Shut-down in period t	{0,1}
$costs$	Total system costs	€
$profit$	Total system profit	€
$revenue$	Total system revenue	€

Objective function: The model maximizes the total profit (revenues minus operational costs) of the setup for a given set of periods (t) as a MILP formulation (3). While revenues (1) are obtained from selling the excess electricity production at the spot market, operational costs (2) consist of: fuel costs, SU and SD fixed costs, carbon emissions costs, cooling of excess heat costs, and the costs of electricity purchases:

$$revenue = \sum_t EP_t \times D_t \times p_{sell_t} \quad (1)$$

$$costs = \sum_t \sum_g \left(C_g^F \times f_{t,g} + C_g^{SU} \times v_{t,g} + C_g^{SD} \times w_{t,g} + C^{CO_2} \times ER_g^{CO_2} \times D_t \times o_{tot_{t,g}} + C^{Q_{Exc}} \times D_t \times q_{exc_{t,g}} \right) + \sum_t EC_t \times D_t \times p_{buy_t} \quad (2)$$

$$\max(profit = revenue - costs) \quad (3)$$

Power balances: The total power output of a unit is defined as the sum of the electric and heat outputs (4). Heat (5) and electric (6) power outputs are expressed as the sum of the respective committed minimum output and the generation above that minimum. Note that this formulation is applied to all generators, including boilers. Electric output variables are fixed to zero for these generators. For CHP units, (7) sets a linear relationship between electric and heat outputs above

minimum: parameter $PQslope_{gc}$ represents the slope of this linear approximation:

$$o_{tot,t,g} = p_{t,g} + q_{t,g} \quad \forall t, \forall g \quad (4)$$

$$q_{t,g} = gq_{t,g} + \underline{Q}_g \times u_{t,g} \quad \forall t, \forall g \quad (5)$$

$$p_{t,g} = gp_{t,g} + \underline{P}_g \times u_{t,g} \quad \forall t, \forall g \quad (6)$$

$$gp_{t,g} = PQslope_{gc} \times gq_{t,g} \quad \forall t, \forall g \quad (7)$$

The heat output of a unit is expressed as the sum of the final dispatch heat flow and the excess heat flow, which must be cooled at the corresponding cooling cost (8):

$$q_{t,g} = q^{fd}_{t,g} + q_{exc,t,g} \quad \forall t, \forall g \quad (8)$$

The electric power balance (9) ensures that the electricity demand equals the electric output of all CHP units plus the difference between power purchased and sold at the spot market. Additionally, the heat balance (10) equals the heat demand with the heat output of all units. Equation (11) defines the fuel consumption as the unit's total energy production divided by the efficiency, which is assumed constant in the entire load range:

$$\sum_{gc} p_{t,gc} + p_{buy_t} - p_{sell_t} = P_{d_t} \quad \forall t \quad (9)$$

$$\sum_g q^{fd}_{t,g} = Q_{d_t} \quad \forall t \quad (10)$$

$$f_{t,g} = o_{tot,t,g} \times D_t / \eta_g \quad \forall t, \forall g \quad (11)$$

Heat pump coupling: When a heat pump is installed downstream of a CHP unit, as proposed in this study, the CHP's thermal power output constitutes the heat source, meaning that heat is transferred to the heat pump's working fluid for evaporation. Condensation occurs in the heat sink, where the working fluid transfers heat to a different water stream, lifting its temperature to the demand requirement. Additionally, the heat pump consumes electricity, which stems from the CHP unit's production.

The heat pump's thermal output is the sum of the committed minimum output and the production above minimum (12). Note that the commitment variable corresponds to that of the CHP unit, meaning that the heat pump is producing whenever the CHP unit is, ensuring that heat is delivered at the required quality:

$$q^{out}_{t,gh} = gq_{t,gh} + \underline{Q}_{gh} \times u_{t,gc} \quad \forall t, \forall gh \quad (12)$$

The heat source input stemming from the CHP unit is defined by means of the heat pump's coefficient of performance (13). The electric power consumption is then obtained by subtracting the heat power output and input flows (14).

$$q^{in}_{t,gh} = q^{out}_{t,gh} (1 - (1/COP_{gh})) \quad \forall t, \forall gh \quad (13)$$

$$p^{in}_{t,gh} = q^{out}_{t,gh} - q^{in}_{t,gh} \quad \forall t, \forall gh \quad (14)$$

The heat pump's electricity consumption reduces the CHP unit's final dispatch volume (15), the main contributor to the

electric power balance (16), which is modified to account for the CHP-heat pump coupling:

$$p_{t,gc} = p^{in}_{t,gh} + p^{fd}_{t,gc} \quad \forall t, \forall gc \quad (15)$$

$$\sum_{gc} p^{fd}_{t,gc} + p_{buy_t} - p_{sell_t} = P_{d_t} \quad \forall t \quad (16)$$

The CHP's heat output constitutes the heat pump's heat source. If existent, the excess heat must be cooled at the corresponding cooling cost (17). Again, the heat pump's thermal output is expressed as the sum of the final dispatch flow and the excess heat (18). Finally, the thermal power balance is modified so that the demand can be covered at the required quality by only the contributions of thermal and heat pump units (19):

$$q_{t,gc} = q^{in}_{t,gh} + q_{exc,t,gc} \quad \forall t, \forall gc \quad (17)$$

$$q^{out}_{t,gh} = q^{fd}_{t,gh} + q_{exc,t,gh} \quad \forall t, \forall gh \quad (18)$$

$$\sum_g q^{fd}_{t,g} = Q_{d_t} \quad \forall t \quad (19)$$

The remaining of the modelling approach draws heavily on the work presented in [7], which introduces a tight and compact formulation for multiple SU and SD trajectories.

Total output: The total power output is modelled for the entire scheduling horizon in (20). It includes the output of CHP and thermal units during the pre-defined SU and SD ramping trajectories. This modelling decision is made to specifically account for the BTC's SU, which includes the biomass gasification process lasting 20 hours [8], during which the BTC remains down. Only one SU and SD trajectory is modelled for each generator. The minimum total output \underline{Q}_g is obtained as the sum of the minimum heat and electric outputs:

$$o_{tot,t,g} = \underline{Q}_g \times (u_{t,g} + v_{t+1,g}) + go_{t,g} + \sum_{i=2}^{D_g^{SD}} O_{g,i}^{SD} w_{t-i+2,g} + \sum_{i=1}^{D_g^{SU}} O_{g,i}^{SU} \times v_{(t-i+D_g^{SU}),g} \quad \forall t, \forall g \quad (20)$$

Modelling of the relationship between commitment, SU and SD variables, as well as constraints on minimum up and down times, operating ramps, and capacity limits, together with initial conditions and their corresponding parameters, are all used as presented on [7]. Finally, eq. (21)-(29) list variable bounds:

$$0 \leq go_{t,g} \leq \bar{O}_g - \underline{Q}_g \quad \forall t, \forall g \quad (21)$$

$$0 \leq gp_{t,gc} \leq \bar{P}_g - \underline{P}_g \quad \forall t, \forall gc \quad (22)$$

$$0 \leq gq_{t,g} \leq \bar{Q}_g - \underline{Q}_g \quad \forall t, \forall g \quad (23)$$

$$0 \leq o_{tot,t,g} \leq \bar{O}_g \quad \forall t, \forall g \quad (24)$$

$$0 \leq p_{t,g} \leq \bar{P}_g \quad \forall t, \forall g \quad (25)$$

$$0 \leq q_{t,g}, q^{fd}_{t,g}, q_{exc,t,g} \leq \bar{Q}_g \quad \forall t, \forall g \quad (26)$$

$$0 \leq q^{out}_{t,gh}, q^{fd}_{t,gh} \leq \bar{Q}_{gh} \quad \forall t, \forall gh \quad (27)$$

$$0 \leq q^{in}_{t,gh} \leq \bar{Q}_{gh} (1 - 1/COP_{gh}) \quad \forall t, \forall gh \quad (28)$$

$$0 \leq p_{buy_t}, p_{sell_t} \leq GCap \quad \forall t \quad (29)$$

2.2 Case Study

To investigate the optimal economic and operational performance of a BTC-heat pump coupling, we apply the proposed formulation to a case study comprising two scenarios:

— *Reference scenario*: we consider an annual series of historical demand data from a chemical processing plant in Spain. It is both heat and electrical intensive and uses three natural gas-driven cogeneration units (CHP 1, 2, 3) to cover their electricity and heat demand, the latter consisting of 21 ton/h of steam (on average) at 12 bar and 190°C. Maximum grid connection capacity is 17 MW for purchase and sale.

— *Proposed scenario*: the three natural gas-CHP setup is replaced by one BTC unit coupled with a high-temperature heat pump to satisfy the same demand series. The heat pump is installed downstream to comply with the required heat quality. A natural gas-fuelled steam boiler is included to assist the heat pump by covering peak hours. Electric power demand is covered by the remaining of BTC’s electricity production not being consumed by the heat pump, together with power purchased from the grid. An overview of the proposed setup is shown in Figure 1. In this case, annualized investment costs of all technologies are included in the final economic evaluation.

Fig. 1 Schematic representation of the proposed scenario plant setup with electricity (solid lines) and heat flows (dashed lines).

The scheduling horizon spans one year (8760 hours) in both scenarios. Day-ahead electricity price data for 2023 is gathered from Spanish TSO Red Eléctrica de España [9], and we assume a 5% increase to obtain the hourly retail prices.

Electricity and heat demand annual profiles are retrieved from the chemical processing plant in hourly resolution. Table 1 presents the technical input parameters used in both scenarios. These data, together with the SU and SD trajectories, are based on the information presented in [8].

A flat cost for natural gas of 39.23 €/MWh is assumed, corresponding to the average cost for 2023 based on market data [10]. For wood chips biomass fuel, we consider a flat cost of 29.40 €/MWh based on [11]. As for carbon emissions, we assume an average cost of 76 €/tonCO₂ for 2023 [12]. Excess heat production is penalized with a cooling cost of 0.6 €/MWh, the result of estimating the electricity consumption of a pump and fan (70 kW each) driving a cooling tower at an average electricity cost.

Table 1 Technical input parameters.

	<i>Reference</i>		<i>Proposed scenario</i>		
	CHP 1,2	CHP 3	BTC	HP	Boiler
\bar{P}/\underline{P} [MW]	4.5/0.5	3.5/0.5	11.8/2.6	-	-
\bar{Q}/\underline{Q} [MW]	8.5/1.5	7.0/1.5	14.9/7.0	15.0/7.0	10.0/2.0
η/COP [per unit]	0.785	0.785	0.900	3.000	0.800
$PQslope$ [per unit]	0.550	0.550	1.159	-	-
RU/RD [MW/h]	48/36	48/36	48/36	-	4/4
UT/DT [h]	4/4	4/4	4/4	-	4/4
ER^{CO_2} [ton/MWh]	0.202	0.202	0.018	-	0.202
D^{SU}/D^{SD} [h]	8/1	8/1	20/1	-	2/1
C^{SU}/C^{SD} [€]	600/300	500/250	692/317	-	200/100

Both model runs are carried out using version 11.0.1 of Gurobi optimization solver [13] under version 6.7.1 of Pyomo [14]. Once the optimization problem is solved, we account for technology investment in the proposed scenario, including BTC, heat pump, boiler, and cooling tower. Power capacities (as shown in Table 1) and their corresponding fixed investment costs (CAPEX) are used as proposed by a technology provider [8] and amount to 58.39 million €. We then calculate the equivalent annual cost (EAC) considering a 5% annual interest rate (r) and 25 years of lifespan (p) using expression (30).

$$Equivalent Annual Cost = \frac{CAPEX}{1 - 1/(1+r)^p} \quad (30)$$

3 Results

This section presents the operational and economic results of the two scenarios considered in the case study. Values shown in Table 2 are the results of the optimization problem solved for the complete scheduling horizon comprising 8760 hours.

Table 2 Case study operational and economic results.

	<i>Reference scenario</i>	<i>Proposed scenario</i>
<i>Operation results</i>		
Electricity dispatch [GWh]	62.8	51.4
Electricity bought [GWh]	6.0	12.8
Electricity sold [GWh]	10.4	5.8
Heat dispatch [GWh]	126.8	126.8
Excess heat [GWh]	0.2	44.1
Renewable dispatch [%]	0.0%	91.3%
Carbon emissions [tonCO ₂]	38,327	6,860
<i>Economic results</i>		
Total operation costs [M€]	-12.97	-8.47
Fuel [M€]	-9.48	-7.52
Carbon emissions [M€]	-2.91	-0.52
Power purchase [M€]	-0.57	-0.38
SU/SD [M€]	-0.01	-0.03
Cooling [M€]	-1x10 ⁻⁴	-0.03
Investment EAC [M€]	0.00	-4.14
Total revenue [M€]	0.83	0.61
Total net profit [M€]	-12.14	-12.00

To show how the demand is satisfied in the proposed scenario, we select two representative weeks: Figures 2a and b show the electricity and heat balance, respectively, for a week with lower electricity costs (October), and a week with higher electricity costs is presented in Figures 2c and d (February). Negative values represent heat pump's electricity consumption (a and c) and BTC's heat export and excess flows (b and d).

When comparing the electricity dispatch results in Table 2, the BTC delivered 18% less electricity than the three CHP units in the reference scenario. Note that the final dispatch volume accounts for the internal demand plus the excess production, which is sold at the spot market. During hours when the units are unable to cover the demand, electricity is bought from the grid. Purchase also happens during hours of low electricity

costs, as shown in Figure 2a (and c, around hour 856). As a result of the BTC having to deliver part of its production to the heat pump, 44% less excess electricity is sold, while purchase volumes are 113% higher compared to the reference scenario.

However, when looking at the economic results, the difference in total revenue associated to the sale of excess electricity is 27% lower than in the reference scenario: this is a result of the model deciding to sell electricity during hours of overall higher prices than in the reference scenario. Moreover, the proposed scenario has lower power purchase costs despite having higher purchase volumes. Again, the model chooses to buy these volumes during hours of overall lower costs.

Fig. 2 Proposed scenario operation profiles: (a) electricity balance, low market costs week, (b) heat balance, low market costs week, (c) electricity balance, high market costs week, (d) heat balance, high market costs week.

Final heat dispatch volumes are equal in both scenarios, meaning that the units can deliver the demanded steam at the required quality. However, when comparing excess heat volumes, the proposed scenario produces considerably higher amounts because of the coupling setup. Figure 2b show that, during hours of low electricity costs, BTC's output is mainly covering the heat pump's electricity and heat inputs, thus reducing excess heat production. This behaviour is also seen in Figure 2d around hour 856, when the steam boiler is off, and the heat pump can solely cover the heat demand.

As a result of the main fuel change from natural gas to biomass, the total renewable dispatch volumes, including electricity and heat, increases to 91.3% in the proposed scenario, and the carbon emissions decrease 82%. In addition to reducing the carbon emissions costs, the main fuel replacement implies also

a reduction in fuel costs, as biomass was, on average, 33% less expensive than natural gas in 2023.

Under the assumptions made in the case study, the proposed scenario has 35% lower operation costs, corresponding to 4.5 million €. Even when considering the annualized investment costs, this scenario ends up having a higher net profit by 0.14 million €, proving that the proposed solution can profitably replace the current setup while covering the medium-temperature industrial heat demand in the required quality.

4 Conclusions

This paper presented a MILP formulation for cogeneration and thermal units providing electricity and heat to industrial users. The formulation features the modelling of a CHP unit coupled

with a high-temperature heat pump, enabling to enhance the quality of heat delivered. A case study involving real industrial electricity and heat demand data was considered to illustrate the mathematical approach. The case study comprised two scenarios in which we studied the replacement of three conventional natural gas-fuelled CHP units by a biomass-fed top cycle coupled with a heat pump for a one-year scheduling horizon. Results showed that the proposed configuration can, firstly, supply the demanded heat in the required quality with decreased carbon emissions, and secondly, achieve lower revenues but with 35% lower operating costs, which makes it a less costly scenario even when annualized investment costs are considered.

To add on to this decarbonization solution, we consider that further research should be carried out to account for additional modelling features. To begin with, the inclusion of different start-up sequences for the cogeneration units could provide more flexibility in the operation, especially for the BTC, whose 20-hour-long start-up ramping includes the biomass gasification process. The modelling of warm and hot start-up sequences could have an impact on the dispatch decisions, enabling quicker transitions from off to on and thus reducing operating costs.

While units' capacities were determined before solving the optimization problem in this case study, the inclusion of sizing modelling in the formulation could be further addressed. This could allow the model to decide the optimal investment and operation decisions simultaneously, providing further valuable results to industrial users.

Moreover, additional revenue streams could be included by modelling the participation in the balancing market by the cogeneration units. Finally, the modelling of varying efficiencies (and coefficients of performance, in the case of heat pumps) with load range, could add value to the formulation.

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